

Part 4 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), novel model simulating screwing of the metallic post inside the root of an endodontically treated tooth, Stupid models for interpreting living organs

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Abstract

Traditional metallic post screw is screw-shaped, including the protocol of screwing, which results in a forceful engagement with the internal root canal wall. This will exert pressure over the root, resulting in straining. Here we want to investigate this very important issue via state of art mechanical testing tool, namely FEA. Results show that the strain led to a deterioration of the root significantly. First mechanical strain, which could be significant, may reach plastic deformation could be ensued before the tooth is even exposed to mechanical load. Poor selection of the material in the case of screw selection would lead to disastrous results

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of bone, jaw weakeners, jaw stiffeners.

Introduction

Traditional metallic post screw shaped, including the protocol of screwing, which results in forceful engagement with the internal root canal wall (1). This will exert pressure over the root, resulting in straining. (2). Here, we want to investigate this very important issue via a state-of-the-art mechanical testing tool, namely FEA. Results show that the strain led to a deterioration of the root significantly. First mechanical strain, which could be significant, may reach plastic deformation could be ensued before the tooth is even exposed to mechanical load. Poor selection of the material in the case of post-selection would lead to disastrous results.

With screwing, we have these results:

- Straining of the dentine within the elastic limit
 - Initiation of variable plastic changes
 - Fracture of the remaining screw and splitting of the root at high insertion torque
 - Accelerated fatigue of the dentine due to strain caused by screwable screw insertion
 - The screw had a very weak in nature attachment to the dentine, which is lost fast after entering function
- The main author had faced a case of a vertical fracture. This is due to high inconsistency across all cases, where some teeth are strong, and others are weak. As well as due to the highly subjective applied torque, which someone could exert a high load and still regard it as small, simply no calibration. The simplest example we can recall here is the screw of the implant connecting screw with a calibrated tool.

An old-fashioned post will include screwing of a metallic screw via a manual driver. In this paper, we want to introduce the effect of the screwing on the dentine. The screw engagement and tightening inside a deformable material, including multiple forces that needed segregated approach. Each element of the associated

mechanical performance should be approached carefully. During screwing, there will be a gradual and forceful pushing of the dentinal walls by the screwing.

Simply, the screw performs wedging inside the canal. This wedging action needs special attention. We had suggested 3 numerical models to simulate the wedging action

- Expansion of the body of the connecting screw
- Splitting the post into 4 pieces and forcing them against the dentine
- Moving the 4-split piece in pre-defined displacement

Splitting the dentine into 4 pieces and compressing them against the connecting screw is another way that we had not evaluated.

Figure 1 This design will lead to enormous strain on the root, which is one of the causes of the fracture.

Figure 2 An ordinary condition that is seen frequently nowadays

In order to comprehend the effect of the screwing on the tooth structure. Modeling the screwing inside soft material is extremely difficult in numerical simulation. Accordingly, we had supposed a model by splitting the screw into 4 pieces or expanding the screw to simplify the wedging action as simple compression against the canal walls. The fracture of the endodontically treated teeth could be related to multifactorial issues. Which could be approached individually

Physical conditions need a segregated approach in the numerical models and simulations.

Methods

We had built our model based on (Mohammed's body for biomechanics in endodontics). This models the basis for all testing related to mechanical issues in endodontics.

Figure 3 Every model starts with a sketch that are number driven.

Figure 4 Every model starts with a sketch that are number driven.

Figure 5 This model could be modified at any tiny feature.

Figure 6 With each turn, the screw will get deeper inside the root canal system, which leads to compression on the walls. We either represent part of the wedging action by displacing the 4 pieces in opposite directions in a predefined way, or place a distraction force. Both boundary conditions are accepted and should be studied deeply.

We had not modeled the crown, as we think there is no need to model the crown here, as the main issue to be solved is the root itself.

Figure 7 This implement movement of the part, 1 in the $-Y$, 2 in the $+X$, 3 in the direction $+Y$, 4 in the direction $+X$

Movements in the Figure 7 will result in a compression on the internal walls of the roots, resulting in significant strain that will exaggerate the next loading in the lateral direction. Again, the engagement of the screw inside the tooth canal system will be lost eventually.

Figure 8 The base of the model is fixed.

Property	Variable	Value	Unit	Property group
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Density	rho	1190[kg/m ³]	kg/m ³	Basic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Young's modulus	E	3.2e9[Pa]	Pa	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Poisson's ratio	nu	0.35	1	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
Coefficient of thermal expansion	alpha_iso ; a...	7.0e-5[1/K]	1/K	Basic
Heat capacity at constant pressure	Cp	1470[J/(kg*K)]	J/(kg.K)	Basic
Thermal conductivity	k_iso ; kii =...	0.18[W/(m*K)]	W/(m.K)	Basic

Figure 9 This is the mechanical properties for the root subdomain and the bone block.

Property	Variable	Value	Unit	Property group
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Density	rho	7850[kg/m ³]	kg/m ³	Basic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Young's modulus	E	205e9[Pa]	Pa	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Poisson's ratio	nu	0.28	1	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
Relative permeability	mur_iso ; m...	1	1	Basic
Electric conductivity	sigma_iso ; ...	4.032e6[S/m]	S/m	Basic
Coefficient of thermal expansion	alpha_iso ; a...	12.3e-6[1/K]	1/K	Basic
Heat capacity at constant pressure	Cp	475[J/(kg*K)]	J/(kg.K)	Basic
Relative permittivity	epsilononr_iso...	1	1	Basic
Thermal conductivity	k_iso ; kii =...	44.5[W/(m*K)]	W/(m.K)	Basic

Figure 10 This is the mechanical properties of the post.

Property	Variable	Value	Unit	Property group
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Density	rho	1190[kg/m ³]	kg/m ³	Basic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Young's modulus	E	3.2e6[Pa]	Pa	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Poisson's ratio	nu	0.35	1	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
Coefficient of thermal expansion	alpha_iso ; a...	7.0e-5[1/K]	1/K	Basic
Heat capacity at constant pressure	Cp	1470[J/(kg*K)]	J/(kg.K)	Basic
Thermal conductivity	k_iso ; kii =...	0.18[W/(m*K)]	W/(m.K)	Basic

Figure 11 This is the mechanical properties of the PD ligament subdomain.

Figure 12 The mesh was excellent with fine parameters.

Figure 13 Mesh parameters for the root and PD ligament subdomain

Figure 14 Mesh creation parameters for other subdomains

Figure 15 In the tooth expansion model, we have represented the root canal system as this need more deeper analysis. Another model needs to be studied (e.i, no root canal system). The blue subdomain was left empty as the stress needs this modification, which is affordable computationally. The model without this canal had not been studied

We had represented 3 models

- Expansion by predefined displacement
- Expansion by force
- Expansion by predefined expansion

This will give the researcher a good ability to select the most accurate physical setting when trying to perform a physical lab study.

Results and discussions

We will limit ourselves to the evaluation of the displacement as a meter for the deformation and stiffness, as well as for the strain, as a more applicable meter that could be applied in the physical lab studies.

Expansion by predefined expansion

Figure 16 In some models, we had fixed the blue region of this model

In the expansion scenario, we had done an expansion of 0.01 in the X and Y direction. One of the very effective capacities of the numerical simulation is limiting the deformation of the body to very confined conditions, which is not applicable in physical lab studies.

Figure 17 We should consider that the root shape is already tapered in shape.

Figure 18 The outer surface displacement could be traced in the physical lab studies.

Figure 19 Strain of the expansion model

Figure 20 This figure represents the inside of the expansion model

Expansion by predefined force

Figure 21 The force application was done in a radially directed force on every 4 segments, resulting in compression on the root subdomain.

Figure 23 The displacement is a different pattern due to a totally different distraction mechanism.

Expansion by predefined displacement

Each segment had a radial displacement of 1 micron

Figure 24 The segmented model is apparent.

Figure 25 Displacement of the displaced model segment

Figure 26 Interior inspection is of paramount importance.

Figure 27 Strain is totally different in distribution and pattern.

Figure 28 We think that this model is the best representing model of the strain that results from the wedging of the screw.

All of the tested models had produced variable effects on the root portion. The results from a real model should be used to tune the digital models and used to match the resulting strain.

References

References

1. *Post-endodontic restorative treatments and their mechanical behavior: A narrative review.* Guilherme Schmitt de Andrade, Guilherme de Siqueira Ferreira Anzaloni Saavedra, Marina Gullo Augusto, Génesis Alfonzo Leon, Hellen Cristina Budel Brandão, João Paulo Mendes Tribst, Amanda Maria de Oliveira Dal Piva. s.l. : Dentistry Review,, 2023.

2. *Metal Posts and the Effect of Material–Shape Combination on the Mechanical Behavior of Endodontically Treated Anterior Teeth.* Gloria, Antonio & Maietta, Saverio & Richetta, Maria & Ausiello, Pietro & Martorelli, Massimo. s.l. : Metals., (2019). .
3. *Effect of teeth periodontium presence on the bone physiology against stiffer status after implant placement or teeth ankylosis event. Teeth as jaw weakeners: a pivotal concept in the biomechanics.* Saadoon, M. Z. (. s.l. : International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), 1(2), 1–33., 2025).
4. *MOHAMMED BODIES' ANALYSIS FEA OF DENTAL IMPLANTS' DESIGN CRITERIA.* Saadoon, M. Z. (2020).

Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024, he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties, as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as a maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, the largest secondary referral center in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.